

Women's Rights in Conflict with People's Cultural Autonomy: Problems of Cultural Accommodation

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Abstract : The paper explores the cultural rights accommodation by the state which has left many unresolved problems. The cultural rights sometimes violate the basic individual rights of the members inside the community like women. The paper further explicates certain cultural norms and practices which violates the rights of women inside the community in the name of culture.

Keywords : women, culture, communities, rights, vulnerable, accomadation

Conference Title : ICCHR 2014 : International Conference on Civil and Human Rights

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : June 26-27, 2014